

Original Article

Montelukast versus Inhaled Corticosteroids in the Management of Mild Persistent Asthma in Children

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Abstract:

Background: Asthma is one of the most common chronic diseases. The prevalence is increasing in Bangladesh, especially among children. Montelukast (MLK) is an orally administered, specific leukotriene receptor antagonist and was the focus of the current study. Although it is important to recognize that inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) use is currently the recommended first-line treatment for asthmatic children, MLK can have consistent benefits in controlling asthmatic symptoms and may be an alternative in children unable to use ICS. This study was done to assess the efficacy of Montelukast versus inhaled corticosteroids in the management of mild persistent asthma in children.

Methodology: This single blind RCT was conducted in asthma center, ICMH, Bangladesh. Patients of mild persistent asthma were enrolled according to National Asthma Guideline from the inpatient and outpatient department. Potential participants were randomly divided into two groups by lottery. One group (A) were given oral montelukast and other group (B) were given inhaled corticosteroid (ICS). The children were followed up for 6 months. The effectiveness of drugs was measured by clinical improvement and lung function test.

Results: The study on children with mild persistent asthma showed oral montelukast as effective as inhaled corticosteroid. There was significant improvement of cough, wheeze, rhonchi, sleep disturbance and PEFr after medication in both groups but the difference in effect between ICS and oral montelukast was found not significant.

Conclusion: This study showed no significant difference between MLK and ICS use in the management of mild persistent asthma in children. Montelukast may be an orally administered safe, effective and cheap alternative to ICS in treating mild persistent asthma, especially in younger children unable to use ICS.

Key words: Mild persistent asthma, Montelukast, Inhaled corticosteroids.

Introduction: Bronchial asthma is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by airway hyper-responsiveness and respiratory symptoms (breathlessness, wheezing, chest tightness and coughing)^{1,2} and the involvement of numerous cell types (eosinophils, T cells, mast cells, basophils and neutrophils) in triggering airway inflammation.³ Anti-leukotrienes are a new

class of anti-inflammatory drugs, which include Montelukast (MLK), Pranlukast, Zafirlukast and Zileuton, with an important glucocorticoids sparing effects. These drugs interfere either with leukotriene receptors (leukotriene receptor antagonists or LTRAs) or with leukotriene production (5-lipoxygenase inhibitors).⁴ Leukotrienes are important proinflammatory

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mediators in asthma. These eicosanoids are derived from the metabolism of membrane phospholipids within alveolar macrophages, eosinophils, mast cells and neutrophils, that are involved in the pathophysiology of this disease.⁵ Cysteinyl leukotrienes cause bronchoconstriction, mucus secretion, increased vascular permeability and eosinophil migration to the airways, and also promote smooth muscle proliferation. Their synthesis and release appear not to be blocked by corticosteroid therapy.⁶⁻¹² MLK is a selective cysteinyl - leukotriene receptor antagonist that reduces asthmatic inflammation and airway resistance and prevents bronchoconstriction.^{3,13-15} It is the most studied and used LTRA in pediatric age, being the first approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the use in young asthmatic children, at the dosage of 4 mg for children aged from 1 to 5 years and of 5 mg for patients 6 to 14 years of age once daily.¹⁶

It was foreseen that antileukotrienes could be used as the first line agents in the management of mild/moderate persistent asthma. A Cochrane review (last updated in January 2004) summarized the accumulating evidence derived from 13 randomized controlled trials and concluded that low doses of inhaled glucocorticoids were superior to LTRAs.⁴

All current international guidelines recommend the use of low-dose (200–400 mcg) of beclomethasone (BDP) or equivalent inhaled corticosteroids (ICSs) as the preferred controller therapy, with LTRAs as an alternative, for the management of persistent asthma in children (5–11 years of age) and adolescents. In patients unresponsive to ICSs alone, the alternative options are the addition of LTRAs or long-acting beta-agonist (LABA), or an increase of ICS dosage.¹⁷⁻²⁰

Also the pediatric PRACTALL guidelines (PRACTicing ALLergy),²¹ in agreement with the GINA (The Global Initiative for Asthma)¹⁸ and the BTS-SIGN (British Thoracic Society Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network)²⁰ guidelines, indicate ICSs as the first choice for controller therapy of pediatric asthma. The authors of BTS-SIGN guidelines recommend the use of LTRA, if ICS cannot be administered. MLK is the most commonly used in children.²² ICSs are used as medication for early intervention and long-term management of childhood asthma, because they directly reach the airways and intensively inhibit airway inflammation.²³⁻²⁵ However, when the amount of drug deposited in the respiratory tract

increases with using higher doses, the risks of adverse drug reactions also increase.^{3,26}

Materials and methods:

This was a randomized control trial (RCT) study conducted in asthma center, ICMH, Bangladesh from 1st March, 2013 to 30th August, 2013. The total sample size was 119 of both sexes from 2-14 years old child. Patients of mild persistent asthma was selected from inpatient and outpatient department with definitive criteria, and then they were invited for participation. Potential participants were randomly divided in two groups by lottery, data was collected by pre-tested structured questionnaire. One group (A) was given oral montelukast and other group (B) was given inhaled corticosteroid (ICS), the outcome and effectiveness of drugs were evaluated by clinical improvement that is night symptom (cough, wheeze, shortness of breath and sleep disturbance), school absenteeism of school going children and lung function test that is peak flow meter. Peak flow meter was done only in children aged ≥ 5 years. Mild persistent asthma was defined as “night time asthma symptoms occurring more than 2 per month but not weekly and may occasionally affect the daily activity or sleep”. The child with congenital heart disease, pulmonary disease like pneumonia, pneumonic consolidation, pleural effusion, pulmonary tuberculosis and cystic fibrosis were excluded. Follow up of both groups was done for at least 3 months and maximum 6 months. Data analysis was done using statistical software SPSS windows version 15.

Results:

Out of 119 children of mild persistent asthma, 63 (53%) patients were given montelukast and 56 (47%) patients given inhaled corticosteroids. A little more than half of the patients (54.6%) were in 5-14 years of age group. Fifty-six percent of at least one parents completed secondary level of education and a little less than half (43.7%) of the family's monthly income was less than ten thousand taka. About half (46.2%) of the families were large in size (4 or more members in a family). The difference between ICS and montelukast group were not significant for any of the sociodemographic characteristics (Table-I). Almost all of the patients (97%) had family history of atopy, a little more than half (59.7%) had family history of asthma and almost half (46.2%) had history of exposure to passive smoking. No significant difference between ICS and montelukast group were found (Table-II).

Cough was present in 100% patient, wheezing and ronchi in almost 100% of patients; 97.5 and 98.3 percent respectively. Night times attack of cough and wheeze was present in 52.1 and 41.2% of cases respectively (Table-III). No significant difference was observed in baseline radiological

findings and lab profile between two treatment groups (Table IV). There was significant improvement after medication in both groups $p < 0.001$ but the difference in effect between ICS and oral montelukast was found not significant $p = 0.722$ (Table-V).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study subjects according to treatment group

Socio-demographic characteristics	Total n (%)	Inhaled corticosteroids n (%)	Montelukast n (%)
Sex			
Male	82(68.9)	38(67.9)	44(69.8)
Female	37(31.1)	18(32.1)	19(30.2)
Age group			
2 up to 5 years	54(45.4)	21(37.5)	33(52.4)
5 years and above	65(54.6)	35(62.5)	30(47.6)
Parents education (at least one or both)			
Illiterate (both)	9(7.6)	4(7.1)	5(7.9)
Primary completed	14(11.8)	9(16.1)	5(7.9)
Secondary and above	67(56.3)	30(53.6)	37(58.7)
Monthly family income			
Less than 10000	52(43.7)	21(37.5)	31(49.2)
10000-20000	38(31.9)	18(32.1)	20(31.7)
Above 20000	29(24.4)	17(30.4)	12(19.0)
Size of the family			
Small family (up to 4 person)	64(53.8)	27(48.2)	37(58.7)
Large family (over 4 persons)	55(46.2)	29(51.8)	26(41.3)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses. p value, significance between ICS and montelukast group obtained by χ^2 test; p value was > 0.05 for all of the sociodemographic characteristics.

Table II: Patients exposure to risk factors - passive smoking, family history of asthma, atopy, presence of pet animal at home and poorly ventilated room according to treatment group.

Risk factors	Total n (%)	Inhaled corticosteroids n(%)	Montelukast n(%)
Passive smoking	55(46.2)	21(37.5)	34(54.0)
Family history of asthma	71(59.7)	34(60.7)	37(58.7)
Presence of atopy	116(97.5)	53(94.6)	63(100.0)
Presence of pet animal at home	4(3.4)	1(1.8)	3(4.8)
Poorly ventilated room	19(16.0)	9(16.1)	10(15.9)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses. p value, significance between ICS and montelukast group obtained by χ^2 test; p value was > 0.05 in all cases.

Table III: Baseline clinical findings of study subjects according to treatment group

Clinical findings	Total n (%)	Inhaled corticosteroids n (%)	Montelukast n (%)
Cough	119(100)	56(100.0)	63(100.0)
Night times attack of cough more than 2 per month but not weekly	62(52.1)	31(55.4)	31(49.2)
Wheeze	116(97.5)	55(98.2)	61(96.8)
Night times attack of wheeze more than 2 per month but not weekly	49(41.2)	22(39.3)	27(42.9)
Not sleep well at night	85(71.4)	40(71.4)	45(71.4)
Absence from school	71(59.7)	37(66.1)	34(54.0)
Vesicular breath sound with prolonged expiration	98(82.4)	49(87.5)	49(77.8)
Ronchi	117(98.3)	56(100.0)	61(96.8)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses. p value, significance between ICS and montelukast group obtained by χ^2 test; p value was > 0.05 in all cases.

Table IV: Base line lab profile and radiological findings of study subjects according to treatment group

Investigations	Total n (%)	Inhaled corticosteroids n (%)	Montelukast n (%)
Raised eosinophil	41(34.7)	19(33.9)	22(35.5)
Eosinophilia in PBF	17(14.3)	6(10.7)	11(17.5)
Raised serum IgE	102(85.7)	47(83.9)	55(87.3)
Increased Translucency	12(10.1)	6(10.7)	6(9.5)
Hyperinflation	55(46.2)	23(41.1)	32(50.8)
Patchy opacity	20(16.8)	9(16.1)	11(17.5)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses. p value, significance between ICS and montelukast group obtained by χ^2 test; p value was > 0.05 in all cases.

TableV: Clinical profile of study subjects before and after giving medication

Clinical characteristics	Before medication n =119, n (%)	After medication n =119, n (%)	P value ¹	Drugs		P value ²
				ICS n = 56	Montelukast n = 63	
Cough	119(100.0)	55(46.2)	<0.001	26(46.4)	29(46.0)	0.965
Night times cough more than 2 per month but not weekly	62(52.1)	15(12.6)	<0.001	8(14.3)	7(11.1)	0.603
Wheeze	116(97.4)	40(33.6)	<0.001	18(32.1)	22(34.9)	0.749
Night times wheeze more than 2 per month but not weekly	49(41.1)	09(7.5)	<0.001	5(8.9)	4(6.3)	0.595
Sleep Disturbance at night	85 (71.4)	42(35.2)	<0.001	19(33.9)	23(36.5)	0.769
Absence from school	71(59.6)	38(31.9)	<0.001	18(32.1)	20(31.7)	0.963
Vesicular breath sound with prolonged expiration	98(82.3)	29(24.3)	<0.001	13(23.2)	16(25.4)	0.782
Ronchi	117(98.3)	30(25.2)	<0.001	13(23.2)	17(27.4)	0.600
PEFR (for >5 yr of age) n = 65						
green zone	11(17)	28(43)		17(43)	11(44)	
yellow zone	28(43)	29(45)		19(47)	10(40)	
red zone	26(40)	8(12)	<0.001*	4(10)	4(16)	0.722

Values expressed as n(%) in parentheses; p value¹, significance of treatment, p value¹ was obtained by McNemar test; P value, significance of treatment on PEFr, P value* was obtained by Wilcoxon signed rank test; P value², significance between ICS and montelukast; p value² was obtained by χ^2 test, as all variables were categorical; 0.05 was considered as level of significance.

Discussion

This RCT study on children with mild persistent asthma showed oral montelukast as effective as inhaled corticosteroid. No significant difference was observed between ICS and oral MLK in the improvement of cough, wheeze, rhonchi, sleep disturbance and PEFr.

Maspero et al. in a 6-month study compared the efficacy of oral MLK with inhaled ICS.²⁷ A total of 124 out of 266 asthmatic children, 6 to 11 years of age, enrolled in the base study, (74 boys, 50 girls) and were re-randomized (2:1 ratio) to receive once-daily oral MLK (n = 83) or ICS (n = 41). Children and their parents showed a significantly higher overall satisfaction for MLK at 6 months than

for ICS (p = 0.001 and p<0.05, respectively); they thought that MLK was more convenient (p<0.001) and less difficult to use (p = 0.005). There was a higher compliance of patients in the MLK group.

In three study (2002, 2005, 2007), Stelmach et al. found no statistical significant differences between MLK and ICSs in clinical and functional parameters in children (6–18 years) treated for 8 weeks, 6 months and 4 weeks respectively. In the first one (91 children) the authors found that after treatment with inhaled triamcinolone and MLK the level of IL-10 in blood serum significantly increased, blood eosinophil counts significantly decreased and all clinical parameters improved.²⁸ In the second one (51 children), they observed that a high dose of inhaled corticosteroid and

MLK significantly decreased levels of total and specific IgE and significantly improved clinical score and FEV1.²⁹ In the third one (87 children), they demonstrated a significant improvement of lung function in all treatment groups.³⁰ Our study also matched with their study.

A handful number of studies comparing the efficacy of oral MLK versus ICSs showed both drugs effective in controlling mild persistent asthma in children without finding any clinical and functional differences between the two drugs.³¹⁻³⁹

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